

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF METHODS FOR MANUFACTURING JUMPERS BY
CONTINUOUS COATING IS SHOWN**

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Abstract: In order to support enterprises in the real sector of the economy, modernization of production, expansion of relations in cooperatives, establishment of strong relations and cooperation, stimulation of demand for products from production in the country's system has a special place.

In this article, in order to carry out investment plans based on the economy and attract investment and loans from foreign countries to the priority sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan, in practice, to develop structural changes in the national economy, the most important Republic of our country needs a favorable environment for investment activities and the necessary It is explained about the existing conditions, the creation of legal norms.

Key words: reinforced concrete, complex, stand technology, foundation, conveyor, cassette method, intermediate plates, vibrating field.

In our country, the experience of involving consistently developing and economically disadvantaged enterprises with all the necessary social and communication infrastructure in the process of rehabilitation has fully justified itself in practice. For this reason, a lot of work is being done in order to liquidate any economically unpromising enterprises operating on the basis of old technology and mechanics and to establish new modern production facilities on their basis [1].

The implementation of the state program was the beginning of our long-term specific work on the construction of housing, social and communal facilities, to radically change and renew the appearance of our cities and villages on the basis of modern architecture and industry. All of these serve to radically improve the quality of life of the country's population and improve the city's conditions.

Materials and methods.

Technological processes in the production of precast concrete and reinforced concrete products consist of a number of independent operations and are combined into separate processes. Operations are conditionally divided into: main, auxiliary and transport types.

The main operations are the preparation of the concrete mixture and the preparation of the materials that make up the mixture; preparation of reinforcement products and finished frames, reinforcement and molding of products; heat treatment of the molded product; it consists of moving the finished product from the mold and preparing the molds for the next cycle, finishing the surface of some products. In addition to the main technological operations, auxiliary operations are also performed at each stage: receiving and transmitting water and steam, compressed air, electricity, storage of raw materials and semi-finished and finished products, quality control of operations and finished products, and performing other main operations necessary steps will be taken.

Stand method. The stand technology is very convenient for the preparation of large-scale large-scale trusses, two-way inclined beams and large-span constructions, columns with a length of more than 12 m. Stretchable products are prepared at the stands. This method is especially effective for pre-stressed products, which are not suitable for production in a hopper-aggregate or conveyor system. The bench method makes it possible to produce products with a wide nomenclature with simple, uncomplicated changes to the equipment.

Two types of stands are used in the production of products: long and short. Long stands (packers) are used when several products are developed simultaneously by the length of the stand. The preparation of the reinforcement package by different methods determines the characteristics of the equipment of the package stands and the level of mechanization of production.

In short stands, one in length, one in width, or two products are often made in a horizontal position (farm, two-slope beam). In short stands, the armature is stretched by electric heating or a hydro jack. Long stands are 70 to 120 m long and are used in general prestressed constructions with a limited load level and in the production of products with a stable nomenclature [6].

In the stand, the armature is stretched by mechanical or electric current. The technological system includes a device that distributes concrete and transfers the concrete mixture to it, a vibrator, vibro stamps or a vibrator and equipment for compacting the mixture of a concrete pourer, equipment and equipment for heat treatment of the product.

Aggregate-flow method The production productivity of the aggregate-flow technological line is determined by the duration of the product molding cycle, and it varies widely depending on the size of the product being molded (5-20 min).

In this method, when the product in the mold is pushed along the line, there is no need to stop at each worker station, but stops only at the stations necessary for the production of the product. In this case, the suspension period may be different for each post. Multi-cavity slabs, single-cavity supports and piles by aggregate technology, poured into individual molds on the vibrafeld, creating cavities without vibromechanism, multi-cavity slabs with the participation of cavity-creators on posts with vibromechanism installed is molded. This method is widely used in the molding of closed and intermediate plates in single or group molds in the vibrofield with load shifter, as well as in molding of flat and ribbed panels, columns, and 7.2m long beams.

Conveyor method Conveyor systems, depending on the type of work, are divided into periodic and non-stop systems, depending on the use of transport - a row of rail or roller conveyor molds, molds forming a continuous steel system or a series of elements and on-board equipment; the arrangement of heat units is horizontal or vertical depending on the surface parallel to the conveyor, as well as in the core of the molding part of the conveyor. The use of conveyor technology in one type of special system (closed and intermediate, internal and external wall panels) is effective mainly for high-capacity factories. It is possible to use the conveyor for simple and reinforced columns and racks, sanitary-technical cabins[4].

The following operations are performed sequentially at the posts of the conveyor system: preparation of the formwork, laying of reinforcement and concrete mixture on it, their distribution and compaction, transfer of the formwork with the product to the continuous heat treatment chamber, removal of the formwork together with the product from the chamber, transfer of the product from the formwork and finished product inspection.

Cassette method. Cassette technology used in the production of reinforced concrete products has a number of advantages and disadvantages. When the product is prepared in cassettes, the precision of the assembled details is achieved, and the concrete surface is flat. As a result of contact heating of concrete, its strength is 10-20% higher than in open formwork. Due to the small open surface of the concrete in the cassette, the temperature rises quickly (60-70°C). The item in the cassette can be heated without holding it first, and the concrete temperature reaches 100°C in cassette devices, and this indicator does not exceed 85-90°C in deep-shaped chambers..

Research results

In the stand method, the product is molded in fixed molds and it hardens in the molded place. At this time, technological equipment and working units are transferred from one mold to another on the stand. Long-sized constructions with tensioned reinforcement can be molded in long stands (75-150 m and longer), as well as in short stands designed for one piece in length and two or more pieces in width. In short stands, the armature is stretched by electric heating or a hydro jack. Long stands are from 70 to 120 m long and are used in general prestressed constructions with limited loading and stable nomenclature. Stands with the length of one or two elements are called short, and stands with the length of 4-15 identical elements are called long stands. In short stands, products are produced with the desired tensioned reinforcement, and in long stands, thin reinforcement with a basic frame is produced.

The production productivity of the unit-flow technological line is determined by the duration of the product molding cycle, and it varies widely depending on the size of the product being molded (5-20 min). It is justified to use the aggregate-flow method in factories for the production of low-volume reinforced concrete products of small and medium capacity. The aggregate method, which is built in a small production area with simple equipment and with low consumption, allows you to obtain a finished product in a volume greater than 1 m² of the production area of the workshop. This method allows you to reset the equipment and switch from one product to another production without excessive costs. Production by the aggregate method includes closed and medium-sized slabs, smooth and ribbed coverings, single and group molds in the vibrofield, preparation of columns, piles, (pile) and rack foundation blocks up to 7.2 m long, non-pressure pipes and sleepers. This method is widely used in the molding of closed and intermediate plates in single or group molds in the vibrofield with load shifter, as well as in the molding of flat and ribbed blocks, columns, and 7.2 m long girders.

The use of conveyor technology in one type of special system (closed and medium, internal and external wall blocks) is effective mainly for high-capacity plants. The conveyor can be used for simple and reinforced columns and racks, sanitary-technical cabins. The number of posts on the conveyor depends on the type of products being produced and their level of finishing (as a rule, they are 6-15). liq. Posts are equipped with machines that perform operations in the technological process. The working rhythm of the conveyor is mainly 10-22 min, and the speed of pushing is 0.9-1.3 m/s [7].

Cassette technology used in the production of reinforced concrete products has a number of advantages and disadvantages. When the product is prepared in cassettes, the precision of the assembled details is achieved, and the concrete surface is flat. As a result of contact heating of concrete, its strength is 10-20% higher than in open formwork. Due to the small open surface of

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Conclusions

Sub-production units of construction sometimes perform the same production functions as plants or factories in industry. It is these organizations that produce the main construction products and, thus, are the first to perform the tasks of launching the main funds and production capacities set before the capital construction. Therefore, the indicators and effectiveness of construction as a branch of the national economy largely depend on the success of these primary construction organizations.

The activities of not only construction organizations, but also customers, design institutions, materials, constructions and equipment suppliers are related to the production of construction products. Such a large number of participants in construction production is not only a distinguishing aspect of construction, but also sometimes becomes a reason for the incomplete success of construction work.

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